

Effect of deep-placed USG containing DAP on grain yield and N and P uptake by transplanted IR36. Greenhouse experiment, IFDC, USA, 1988.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield ^b (g/4 hills per box)	Uptake by grains ^b (g/4 hills per box)	
		N	P
Check	97 c	1.30 e	0.16 d
USG deep placed at transplanting	130 b	1.78 cd	0.18 d
TSP incorporated before transplanting	128 b	1.61 d	0.31 ab
PU+DAP incorporated before transplanting	150 a	1.93 abc	0.32 a
DAP incorporated before transplanting + PU topdressed at panicle initiation	152 a	2.04 ab	0.31 ab
DAP incorporated before transplanting + remaining N as USG deep placed at transplanting	150 a	1.89 bc	0.34 a
TSP incorporated before transplanting + USG deep placed at transplanting	157 a	2.13 a	0.26 bc
USG containing DAP deep placed at transplanting	152 a	2.06 ab	0.26 c
PAPR incorporated before transplanting + USG deep placed at transplanting	147 a	2.07 ab	0.24 c

^aRates of application: 19.3 mg N and 10.3 mg P/kg soil; 619 mg N and 329 mg P/4 hills per box. Estimated rate (on area basis), 40 kg N and 21 kg P/ha. One USG was placed at 110-cm depth in the center of 4 rice hills with 20*20-cm spacing. Incorporation means broadcast and incorporation up to 5-cm depth before transplanting with practically no floodwater. Fertilizer analysis: PU and USG, 46% N; DAP, 21.2% N and 23.5% P; TSP, 20.9% total P; and PAPR from Central Florida (25% acidulation with H₃PO₄, 15.0% total P. ^bMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Plant growth the first 3-4 wk after transplanting was markedly slower for deep-placed USG containing DAP (see table). However, grain yields and N and P uptake were statistically on a par with those for incorporated DAP, TSP, or partially acidulated phosphate rock (PAPR) and deep-placed USG. The PAPR used was as effective as TSP in P availability.

These data suggest that deep-placed USG containing appropriate amounts of DAP may be a judicious choice as a NP fertilizer for small farmers in transplanted rice areas, especially rainfed, where adequate incorporation of fertilizers is not possible because of uncontrolled floodwater and nonavailability of suitable implements. Research under field conditions is under way in India to verify this. ■

Rate and time of N application for direct seeded irrigated rice

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We evaluated rate and time of N application for irrigated rice on a clay loam soil. Soil had pH 7.3 and 0.42% organic C. Treatments were N at 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha in kuruvai (Jun-Sep) and 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg/ha in thaladi (Oct-Feb) and samba (Sep-Jan) seasons, and the initial half of the N applied at four different times in kuruvai (at 10, 20, 30 d after seeding [DAS] and at active tillering) and at five different times in thaladi and samba (at sowing; 10, 20, 30 DAS; and at active tillering). The remaining 50% of N was applied in two equal doses at active tillering and panicle initiation stages, except in treatments where the initial dose itself was applied at active tillering. In this treatment, N was applied in two splits, half at active tillering and half at panicle initiation.

N was broadcast as urea. Basal fertilizer was incorporated in dry soil during kuruvai and samba when dry seeding was done, and in the puddle

Yield and panicles/m² of direct seeded rice with graded rates and time of N application, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Kuruvai		Thaladi		Samba			
	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
N rate (kg/ha)								
	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Samba					
0		0	289	2.5	236	1.6	307	3.2
40		50	327	4.3	308	2.8	374	4.5
80		100	362	5.0	332	3.3	434	5.1
120		150	383	5.2	351	3.5	453	5.3
LSD (0.05)			10	0.2	25	0.15	17	0.15
Time of application (initial 50% N)								
At sowing		-	-	-	328	3.1	421	4.9
10 DAS			356	4.8	343	3.5	434	5.0
20 DAS			384	5.4	339	3.3	470	5.5
30 DAS			346	4.7	325	3.1	398	4.7
At tillering			343	4.4	317	3.0	378	4.6
(LSD 0.05)			12	0.2	ns	0.19	22	0.19

during thaladi when wet seeding was done. Water was maintained at 2-3 cm for topdressing.

The experiments were laid out in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Short-duration TKM9, medium-duration IR20, and long-duration CR1009 were sown in kuruvai, thaladi, and samba, respectively. Dry seeds were broadcast during kuruvai and samba; sprouted seeds were broadcast on puddled soil in thaladi.

In general, yields increased with N application in all three seasons (see table). The responses to N application fitted quadratic functions.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Kuruvai } Y &= 2.6 + 0.05 N - 0.0003 N^2 \\ \text{Thaladi } Y &= 1.6 + 0.03 N - 0.0001 N^2 \\ \text{Samba } Y &= 3.1 + 0.03 N - 0.0001 N^2 \end{aligned}$$

The initial 50% N could be applied 20 DAS in kuruvai and samba when dry seeding was done, and 10 DAS in thaladi when sprouted seeds were sown in puddled soil. ■